

Actual vs Predicted (AverageSunHours)

Standardized Residuals (AverageSunHours)

Partial Regression Plot (AverageSunHours)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.2571$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 1.9425

p-value: 0.1634

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 5.4832

df: 2

p-value: 0.0645

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (AverageSunHours)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – AverageSunHours

